

poiesis
TRUST IN SCIENCE

D4.1: Recruitment and engagement strategy

Authors: *Panagiotis Kavouras (NTUA), Leonidas Ananiadis (NTUA), Nikol Sarla (NTUA), Richard Woolley (CSIC)*

Reviewer: *Martin W. Bauer (LSE)*

Editors: *Costas A. Charitidis (NTUA), Serge P.J.M. Horbach (AU)*

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Author:	<i>Panagiotis Kavouras (NTUA), Leonidas Ananiadis (NTUA), Nikol Sarla (NTUA), Richard Woolley (CSIC)</i>
Reviewer:	<i>Martin W. Bauer (LSE)</i>
Editor(s):	<i>Serge P.J.M. Horbach (AU), Costas A. Charitidis (NTUA)</i>

ABSTRACT:	POIESIS, being a RIA project, is heavily dependent on the collection of secondary and primary data, through the implementation of seven different types of engagement activities, namely Expert workshops, Deliberative workshops, Expert interviews, Survey experiments, Focus groups, Open deliberative roundtable workshops, and a Scenario workshop. These engagement activities must be implemented within the three-year duration of the project, posing substantial challenges to the successful recruitment of all participants required. This deliverable presents the internal procedure that is going to be implemented by the POIESIS beneficiaries, to ensure the recruitment of all relevant stakeholders, for all planned engagement activities. This internal procedure is codified in the deliverable's title, "Recruitment and engagement strategy", and will be supervised by the Permanent Recruitment and Engagement Working Group (PREWG).
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Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	AARHUS UNIVERSITY	AU	Denmark
2.	Partner	WISSENSCHAFT IM DIALOG GGMBH	WiD	Germany
3.	Partner	NATIONAL TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS	NTUA	Greece
4.	Partner	INSTITUTO UNIVERSITÁRIO DE LISBOA	ISCTE	Portugal
5.	Partner	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE	CNRS	France
6.	Partner	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC	Spain
7.	Associated partner	LONDON SCHOOL OF ECONOMICS AND POLITICAL SCIENCE	LSE	UK

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1 Introduction

1.1 The POIESIS project

In a context where societal dependence on sound scientific research and responsible innovation has become increasingly visible, concerns about public trust and mistrust in science have simultaneously been mounting among various types of stakeholders connected directly (e.g. researchers, research funders, research administrators, research policy makers, members of research ethics committees and research integrity offices) or indirectly (e.g. science journalists, lay people) with the research enterprise. Pressing global and local challenges cannot be adequately addressed without reliance on valid evidence and innovation uptake. Hence, the cultural authority of science, research, and innovation – the confidence and trust that citizens and societal actors place in science, research, and innovation – is of crucial importance. This project, entitled “Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science” (POIESIS), will systematically develop a knowledge base about trust in science, including detailed examination of how patterns of trust relate to the alignment of research practices with fundamental principles of research integrity on the one hand and the integration of citizens and societal actors in research practices on the other hand.

POIESIS is concerned with the creation or making of knowledge in responsible ways as well as with the consequences of (ir)responsible practices for stages of knowledge utilisation, verification and adoption. We examine research integrity and societal integration as prominent vehicles for responsible knowledge creation. We recognise the obvious intrinsic value of conducting research in accordance with appropriate ethical, legal, and professional frameworks, obligations, and standards, on the one hand, and with the integration of relevant societal stakeholders in all phases of the research cycle on the other hand. However, we tailor our conceptual and empirical research programme to focus specifically on the impact of such responsible (or irresponsible) research practices in terms of societal trust. Our intention is to systematically examine the impact of research integrity and society’s integration in research on societal trust in research and innovation (R&I).

The overarching research objective of POIESIS is to understand how, and to what extent, societal trust in science, research, and innovation is affected by the aligning of research practices with principles of research integrity and by the integration of citizens and societal stakeholders in different phases of the research cycle. Moreover, the project aims to understand how institutions, particularly Research Performing and Research Funding Organisations, can foster research practices that are, in turn, conducive to enhancing public trust in science. Our goal is to develop evidence-based recommendations for tackling societal mistrust and for strengthening the societal co-creation of research; ultimately contributing in the long-term perspective to increased public trust in science and increased alignment of research with societal needs, expectations, and values.

The evidence-base produced by the project will enable us to contribute to the following specific objectives:

1. To provide recommendations for policy makers, research funding and performing organisations, higher education institutions and other R&I actors for tackling societal mistrust in science, research and innovation;
2. To provide recommendations to research performing and funding organisations, for strengthening the co-creation of research and innovation contents by society, and for the spreading of good practices and evidence of their effects; and
3. To implement innovative means of communicating and disseminating the findings and messages of our research.

The key output from POIESIS will be policy recommendations for tackling societal mistrust in science and for strengthening the co-creation of R&I contents by society. A core set of general recommendations, relevant for all end-users, will be extended by sets of user-specific recommendations tailored to their needs. All POIESIS recommendations will be packaged together in an accessible and attractive format, tailored to the specific needs of diverse actors, thereby promoting mutual understanding among R&I stakeholders.

1.2 About this deliverable

This document describes the recruitment and engagement strategy to be applied throughout the duration of POIESIS. The successful implementation of the project's empirical programme is heavily reliant on the timely and efficient recruitment of stakeholders. Work packages (WPs) 1-3 call for continuous recruitment efforts, since the co-creation events will run throughout the POIESIS timeline. In addition, WP4 will recruit stakeholders for the co-creation of the project's policy recommendations during a scenario workshop that is going to take place close to the end of POIESIS.

As set out in the POIESIS Grant Agreement, *“the overall objective of WP4 is to develop and implement a robust and ambitious plan for recruiting and engaging core stakeholders to become involved in POIESIS research activities, and for widely disseminating and communicating POIESIS activities, findings, and outputs to optimize uptake and exploitation of POIESIS recommendations and to contribute to the sustainability of POIESIS outcomes”*. For this to come into being, the POIESIS consortium set up a Permanent Recruitment and Engagement Working Group (PREWG), led by NTUA, during the Kick off Meeting (KoM) held in Aarhus in M1 (8-9 of September 2022). The recruitment efforts will be guided and supported by a comprehensive Dissemination and Exploitation Plan including Communication activities (DEPC), D4.2, to be delivered in M4 (31 December 2022).

This report starts with a section that describes the project's needs with regard to stakeholder recruitment and continues with the presentation of the composition, the *modus operandi*, and the initial action plan of the PREWG. It then describes the use of the DEPC for the facilitation and boosting of recruitment activities and the engagement of stakeholders that goes beyond their participation in the planned co-creation events of the project. This deliverable concludes with the description of the methodology for the Scenario workshop that will occur toward the end of the project.

2 Recruitment needs

This section contains the POIESIS “recruitment cards”. These cards are a means to codify a number of specific data, including the date an engagement event will take place, the recruitment needs, and the number of stakeholders' required to participate. These recruitment cards will provide an easy-to-use way for the PREWG to follow recruitment progress for the different engagement activities of POIESIS. These cards will act as short guiding notes to all POIESIS beneficiaries that will be involved in the recruitment processes. The cards will be filled with the needed information by the PREWG, as soon as all protocols will have been finalised. The filled recruitment cards will be updated by the PREWG in case of a change in the recruitment strategy or recruitment goals. The template for the recruitment card is shown below:

RECRUITMENT CARD

template

1. How many in total?

The number of engagement events of a specific type that is going to be organised, based on the relevant protocol of the relevant WP.

2. When?

Date(s) of the engagement events, based on the Grant Agreement of POIESIS.

3. Period for recruitment

Dates for the commencement and conclusion of the recruitment process for the specific engagement event(s).

4. Where?

Place(s) that this event will take place, based on the Grant Agreement of POIESIS and the relevant WP protocol.

5. Type(s) of stakeholder(s)?

Type(s) of stakeholders planned to participate, based on the relevant WP protocol.

6. How many stakeholders per event and how many in total?

The number of participants for each different engagement event and the total number of participants in all events of the same type, based on the relevant WP protocol. The latter information is relevant only in the cases where the same type of event is going to take place more than once (e.g. in more than one country).

7. Purpose?

A brief description of the aims of this type of engagement event.

The remainder of this section presents preliminary recruitment cards for all types of engagement events.

2.1 Expert workshops (WP1) - WID

RECRUITMENT CARD

for Expert Workshops

1. How many in total?

3 expert workshops.

2. When?

M8 (April 2023), M16 (December 2023), and M24 (August 2024)

3. Where?

Central European locations (to be decided).

4. Period for recruitment

M5-M7, M13-M15, M21-M23 (Tentative)

5. Type(s) of Stakeholder(s)?

International group of academics and other professionals with extensive knowledge about indicator development in the areas of concern for POIESIS.

6. How many stakeholders per event?

±10 stakeholders for the first and second workshop; ±15 for the final workshop.

7. Purpose

The first workshop will focus on discussing our approach to securing, integrating, and validating data sources and indicators for POIESIS purposes. The second expert workshop on data will be aimed at presenting early analyses of the data and engaging the experts in proposing and co-creating analytical strategies to refine our work. The third workshop will discuss, challenge, and improve results and syntheses across the different data streams.

2.2 Deliberative workshops (WP2) - ISCTE

RECRUITMENT CARD

for Deliberative workshops

1. How many?

7 deliberative workshops, 1 in each consortium country

2. When?

M10-M12 (June-August 2023)

3. Where?

At a central location in each of the seven POIESIS consortium member countries

4. Period for recruitment

M6-M9 (Tentative)

5. Type(s) of stakeholder(s)?

Volunteer participants chosen to represent voices from different social groups, taking into account socio-demographic characteristics including gender, education, professional role, and with a view to including minorities and under-represented voices in science.

6. How many stakeholders?

40 in each deliberative workshop, 280 in total

7. Purpose?

To explore whether concerns about a lack of scientific integrity and societal integration affect public trust, how people choose media and messages, and how they use and see traditional and new media as means of scientific authority. In addition to explore desirable ways to integrate citizens and other stakeholders in the research cycle.

2.3 Expert interviews (WP2) - CSIC

RECRUITMENT CARD

for Expert Interviews

1. How many?

112 interviews in the consortium, 16 interviews in each consortium country

2. When?

M20-22 (April-June 2024)

3. Where?

In each consortium country and/or online

4. Period for recruitment

M17-M19 (Tentative)

5. Type(s) of stakeholder(s)?

Mediators (10 for each country), topical expert researchers (3 for each topical area per country)

6. How many stakeholders?

112

7. Purpose?

To understand in deeper detail the views of the ‘supply’ side on how (ir)responsible research practices can best be communicated and how that might affect public trust in science.

2.4 Survey experiment (WP2) - AU

RECRUITMENT CARD

for Survey Experiment

1. How many?

The survey experiment will be fielded as a series of studies across all consortium member countries.

2. When?

M23-25 (July – September 2024)

3. Where?

In each of the POIESIS consortium countries

4. Period for recruitment

M20-M22

5. Type(s) of stakeholder(s)?

Lay people

6. How many stakeholders?

The survey aims to recruit 50 participants per experimental condition per country, amounting to 450 participants per country.

7. Purpose?

To investigate how research practices influence levels of trust in science in the population, aiming to produce large-scale experimental data specifically tailored to provide evidence on institutional impact on public trust in science.

2.5 Focus groups (WP3) – CNRS + National co-investigators

RECRUITMENT CARD

for Focus Groups

1. How many?

21 Focus Groups in the consortium, 3 in each consortium country

2. When?

M16-18 (December 2023 - February 2024)

3. Where?

In each consortium country

4. Period for recruitment

M13-M15 (Tentative)

5. Type(s) of stakeholder(s)?

Institutional stakeholders (i.e. researchers, research leaders and managers in RPOs, Research Integrity Officers, and institutional communication experts)

6. How many stakeholders?

6-10 in each Focus Group, 18-30 in each country, 126-210 in total

7. Purpose?

Set a basis for organising the structure of the Deliberative Roundtable discussions in the next task, the open deliberative workshops.

2.6 Open deliberative roundtable workshops (WP3) – CSIC

RECRUITMENT CARD

for Open Deliberative Workshops

1. How many?

7 in the consortium, 1 in each consortium country

2. When?

M24-26 (August – October 2024)

3. Where?

In each consortium country

4. Period for recruitment

M21-M23 (Tentative)

5. Type(s) of stakeholder(s)?

Different types of experts will be mobilised during this round table, initially building on the set of participants engaged in the Focus Groups

6. How many stakeholders?

140 (20 in each consortium country), mainly consisting of the people who have taken part in the project's Focus Groups.

7. Purpose?

To decompartmentalise the discussions that took place at the FGs and to bring together different stakeholders, regardless of their institutional affiliation.

2.7 Scenario workshop (WP4) – NTUA

RECRUITMENT CARD

for Scenario Workshop

1. How many?

1 workshop

2. When?

M34 (June 2025)

3. Where?

Brussels (provisional)

4. Period for recruitment

M29-M33 (Tentative)

5. Type(s) of stakeholder(s)?

Participants from the national-level research activities (10-15) and policy actors at international level (10-15), representing, e.g., international networks of RPOs, RFOs, national academies and learned societies, research ethics and research integrity networks, industry, and members of the European Parliament and the European Commission involved in research and innovation policy.

6. How many stakeholders?

20-30

7. Purpose?

To co-create with stakeholders and policy-makers the final POIESIS policy recommendations for tackling societal mistrust in science and for strengthening the co-creation of R&I contents by society.

3 The permanent recruitment and engagement working group (PREWG)

During the POIESIS KoM the consortium decided on the composition of the PREWG, on its *modus operandi*, and on a preliminary action plan. This section presents the decisions that were made during the KoM.

3.1 Composition

The PREWG includes two members of the Coordinating team (Aarhus), all WP leaders and three additional members. The composition of the PREWG is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The composition of the PREWG.

Name	Role	Entity
Niels Mejlgaard	Coordinator	AU
Serge Horbach	WP5 leader	AU
Ricarda Ziegler	WP1 leader	WID
Panagiotis Kavouras	WP4 leader	NTUA
Leonidas Ananiadis	WP4 member	NTUA
Marta Entradas	WP2 leader	ISCTE
Michel Dubois	WP3 leader	CNRS
Richard Woolley	WP4 member	CSIC
Martin W. Bauer	WP1 member	LSE

3.2 *Modus operandi*

The **PREWG** will convene during the Executive Board meetings via physical or online presence, depending on the planning that has been made by the coordinators. The first meeting will take place in Berlin, Germany on the 26th of January, where the next Executive Board has been scheduled. This will be an important milestone for the PREWG, since by then all protocols will have been submitted as deliverables (D1.1 and D2.1) or will be under the final stages of preparation (D3.1). As a result, the members of the PREWG will have a more detailed view (than the one described in the Grant Agreement) of the specific needs of each engagement event.

The **leaders of WP4 and the coordinators** (all of which are members of the PREWG) will convene via online means also in the period in between two successive Executive Board meetings, in order to monitor whether all recruitment processes are going according to the plan that is described in the Recruitment Cards and Recruitment Monitoring Cards. As a result, the monitoring exercise will be supervised and adapted (if needed) on a monthly basis. More specifically, adaptations of the

recruitment process and engagement strategy will be refined during these meetings by monitoring the recruitment targets and adapt them in case any shortcomings in the recruitment effectiveness have been identified.

The **leaders of WP4** will be in constant interaction with all partners that will be responsible for applying the recruitment procedures in their countries. They will keep track of all active recruitment processes, in order to report to the coordinators or to the PREWG during the scheduled meetings.

3.3 Action plan

For successful recruitment and to achieve participation of the needed type(s) and numbers of stakeholders, each different engagement process will have a “Recruitment Monitoring card”. The Recruitment Monitoring cards will provide a way to monitor the progress of the recruitment process. Each POIESIS beneficiary will fill its own Recruitment Monitoring card, for the engagement events that will take place simultaneously in all POIESIS consortium countries. For the events that will not take place in all POIESIS consortium countries (i.e. Expert WSs and Scenario WS) these cards will be filled by the WP leader responsible for these events.

The template of this card is presented below, together with a short explanation of the different fields it contains:

RECRUITMENT MONITORING CARD

- **Commencement of recruitment activities:** This field will contain the date that recruitment activities for a specific engagement event have to initiate. The initiation date has to take into account the type(s) and number of stakeholders that have to be recruited. More specifically, based on the experience from previous projects, researchers can be recruited more easily than policy makers, lay publics and other non-academic actors. As a result, the involved POIESIS partners may have to initiate the recruitment of the latter stakeholders earlier than the recruitment of researchers. In addition, the involved POIESIS partners, again based on their prior experience, will take into account the anticipated likelihood of different types of stakeholders accepting participation invitations, in order to define the number of stakeholders that have to be invited for an engagement event.
- **Beneficiaries involved (in addition to the PREWG):** This field will contain the individual POIESIS partners that will be involved in the specific recruitment process.
- **Networks to be contacted:** Based on D4.2 the PREWG will define the networks/institutions/individuals that are going to be contacted for recruitment.
- **Entities to expand the reach out of recruitment:** This field gives information about the potential networks that could amplify recruitment efforts, for example networks that POIESIS members have established relations with in previous projects.
- **Updates on the recruitment progress:** The PREWG will meet regularly in order to assess the progress of the recruitment. This will happen during the Executive Board (EB) meetings, but if needed the PREWG will meet also in between consecutive EB meetings.

The utility of the Recruitment Monitoring cards is to help consortium partners to collect information regarding the recruitment progress in a homogeneous way, in order for the PREWG to be able to compile the progress during its planned meetings. In a way, the Recruitment Monitoring cards provide guidance to POIESIS partners to produce the same type of data relevant to the progress of the

recruitment process. These cards, when filled, will be sent to the PREWG, in due time before each planned meeting, in order for NTUA to compile a clear overview of the overall progress of the recruitment. This will help the members of the PREWG to decide, if needed, on contingency measures, in case the recruitment progress lacks the necessary effectiveness. The structure of the Recruitment Monitoring cards will be revised taking into account the experiences of the recruitment, i.e. new fields might have to be added or existing fields may have to be removed, for the sake of effectiveness and efficiency, so as not to unnecessarily increase the work effort to POIESIS partners.

Figure 1: Timeline of all POIESIS engagement events that are presented by different coloured bars or with arrows. A ribbon has been placed below the horizontal axis to delineate the calendar year. The acronyms are explained in the text below.

Figure 1 above presents an overview of the planned engagement events, per year. In all cases the recruitment period extends 3-4 months prior to the start of each engagement event. As a result the recruitment process for the first stage of the Expert Workshops is bound to start early in 2023, i.e.

January or February. The acronyms in Figure 1 are as follow: WS: Workshop, ODW: Open Deliberative Workshop.

4 Utilisation of dissemination and communication tools

WP4's description in the POIESIS Grant Agreement contains the following: “develop a strategy and roadmap for how to keep research participants engaged with POIESIS to become part of a network of stakeholders, who will also be of crucial importance in relation to the project's dissemination and communication objectives.” POIESIS will implement its DEPC (D4.2) not only to inform relevant stakeholders and lay people on the progress and outputs of the project, but also to create a network of stakeholders with an active role that will act as a magnifying lens for dissemination and communication.

Since the above aim transcends the conventional dissemination and communication activities an EU-funded project usually has to apply, POIESIS beneficiaries elaborated the foreseen dissemination and communication measures that were described in section 2.2 of the POIESIS Grant Agreement. The table below specifies the use of the project's communication channels (partially based on Table 2.4 of the Grant Agreement). NTUA is responsible for providing content to the project's website and Social Media channels. When needed, NTUA will provide informative material for public outreach activities that will be adapted to the needs of the specific event and will be drafted according to the POIESIS branding (please refer to D4.3).

Table 2: Main communication channels to be used for boosting the recruitment per engagement event.

Dissemination, Communication channel		Engagement/Co-creation type						
		Expert WSs	Delib. WS	Expert interviews	Survey experiments	Focus groups	Open delib. WSs	Scenario WS
Branding: Logo, color set and choice of typography.			×		×		×	
Website: The POIESIS website.			×		×		×	
Social media: LinkedIn and Twitter.		×	×	×	×	×	×	×
Conferences: Participation in conferences.		×		×	×	×		×
Workshops: Participation in relevant running EU-funded project workshops/events.		×		×	×	×		×
Public outreach events: Participation in open/public events.			×				×	

Press releases: Press releases, targeting newspapers.			×				×	×
Printed material: Newsletters and brochures.			×				×	
Scientific publications: Publications in peer reviewed journals.		×		×	×	×		

5 Scenario workshop

5.1 Aims and objectives

POIESIS, in the context of Task 4.4, will design, prepare, and implement a European-level Scenario workshop in M34, i.e. in June 2025. The aim of the Scenario workshop is to co-create with stakeholders, with a focus on policy makers, the final POIESIS policy recommendations for tackling societal mistrust in science and for strengthening the co-creation of R&I contents by society. The Scenario workshop will use as input the recommendations that are going to be developed in the context of WP1, WP2 and WP3 and which will be reported in the deliverables: D1.5: Integrity, integration, and institutions for trust: Recommendations based on evidence from secondary data sources; D2.5: Cultivating chains of mediation to foster trust in science: Recommendations; and D3.4: How can institutions promote responsible research to enhance trust in science: Recommendation.

The Scenario workshop will include two types of participants:

- Stakeholders from national-level research activities (10-15 participants). The specific types of stakeholders to be invited will be decided on the basis of the results of D1.5, D2.5, and D3.4.
- Policy actors at the international level, representing international networks of research performing organisations (e.g. LERU, the GUILD, EUA), research funding organisations (e.g. Science Europe), national academies and learned societies (e.g. ALLEA), and research ethics and research integrity networks (e.g. ENRIO, EUREC), but we will also engage members of the European Parliament and the European Commission involved in research and innovation policy (10-15 participants).

The WP4 leader is responsible for organising the Scenario workshop, both in methodological and in practical terms.

5.2 What a Scenario workshop is

The European Awareness Scenario Workshop (EASW) methodology was developed by the INNOVATION program, launched in 1994, aiming at the exploration of new actions and social experiments (European Awareness Scenario Workshops, 1997). The central idea of the EASW is the statement of a *problem* and the quest for a *solution* based on participatory planning. By discussing different scenarios the participants in the workshop identify the expected obstacles and possible solutions to a problem.

The EASW is focused on the circulation of ideas among participants from different backgrounds, resulting in designing scenarios and concrete actions. With the discussion and the opportunity of exchanging experiences between representatives of different components of society, where every participant is regarded as an expert operating at a local level, new knowledge, ideas, and policy proposals are developed (City Council of Naples, 2011). The collaboration between various local actors aims at balancing the relationship between society, technology, and the environment.

In the POIESIS context the Scenario workshop will circulate ideas to participants, half of them being policy actors, while the other half will be other types of stakeholders. As described in the proposal text, this selection of stakeholders aims to elevate the national-level discussions, deliberations, results, and recommendations to the European level.

The scenarios are possible visions and views developed when confronting a specific problem and looking for a solution, regarded as different methods to manage the arising issues. The scenarios are constructed by identifying the key variables and by considering the roles of the different actors involved, i.e. by identifying the components of the scenario prone to change, as well as the likely influences on the direction of change (Oreszczyn & Carr, 2008).

In the EASW methodology, there are two approaches to scenario creation: either the participants, working in break-out groups, during the first part of the workshop create the scenarios after being supplied with directions, or the scenarios are written beforehand by the organisers of the workshop. Given the fact that the scenarios are regarded as possible solutions to specific problems, as such they can state new ways of organising and managing certain problems. The scenarios written beforehand must be different from those constructed by participants on two levels: firstly, with respect to the technical and organisational solutions described and, secondly, with respect to the social and political values embedded in them (Andersen & Jæger, 1999). In this way, the participants are provided with multiple solutions and, consequently, multiple realities to explore for possible proposals.

5.3 Format and setting

In the POIESIS project, as stated in the proposal, the scenarios will be written beforehand and provided to the participants. The scenarios will be informed by the results of D1.4: Consolidated OA data set for responsible research practices and trust in science; D1.5: Integrity, integration, and institutions for trust: Recommendations based on evidence from secondary data sources; D2.5: Cultivating chains of mediation to foster trust in science: Recommendations, and; D3.4: How can institutions promote responsible research to enhance trust in science: Recommendations.

The Scenario workshop will comprise of two main parts. The **first part** will consist of break-out groups followed by a plenary session, which aims at the specification of the themes to be discussed in the second part. The **second part** will consist of thematic groups discussing the themes identified in the first part, followed by a plenary session to decide on the best proposals for action. The participants will carry out assessments of the policy recommendations that will address the problems stated in the scenarios. Subsequently, the participants will develop visions for future solutions, and concrete proposals for realizing these solutions (Andersen & Jæger, 1999). Figure 2 provides a flow chart of the Scenario workshop and Table 3 provides a tentative agenda of the workshop, with the duration of each session.

5.3.1 Before the Scenario workshop

The creation of the scenarios is going to take place after the submission of deliverables D1.5, D2.5, and D3.4, which are due in M30, i.e. four months before the implementation month of the Scenario workshop. Based on these deliverables and also on D1.4, which is due in M24, NTUA will create two main discussion topics; in addition, for each topic at least two best-case and two worst-case scenarios are going to be developed. NTUA will circulate them to the members of the Executive Board, in order to receive feedback on which main discussion topic and which different scenarios would be the most appropriate to be fed into the Scenario workshop.

The main discussion topic(s) and the relevant best-case and worst-case scenarios will be circulated to the participants two weeks before the Scenario workshop, i.e. within M33 (May 2025).

5.3.2 Practical issues

The Scenario workshop will take place in Brussels, Belgium. This selection has been based on two main reasons: (a) Brussels is centrally located in Europe, with good connection via various means of transport, thus facilitating the access of participants; (b) Important policy actors from organisations/institutions like the European Parliament, European Parliament's Science and Technology Options Assessment (STOA) Panel, and the European Commission are located in Brussels, facilitating their participation. In addition, other stakeholders are also located in Brussels, like the European University Association (EUA), the Guild of European Research-Intensive Universities (GUILD), and the European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (EARMA). Other important organisations are located conveniently close to Brussels, like the League of European Research Universities (LERU) that is located in Leuven, Belgium, ALL European Academies (ALLEA) that is located in Berlin, Germany, and the European Network of Research Ethics Committees (EUREC) that is located in Bonn, Germany.

The Scenario workshop will be facilitated by three members of the NTUA and two member of the AU team. Out of these five POIESIS consortium members, one will have the overall responsibility for the workshop and will facilitate the introduction, the plenary, and the wrap-up sessions. The other four will facilitate the discussions during the break-out and thematic group sessions.

5.3.3 First part: Vision making

In the Scenario workshop's **first part**, the break-out groups will consist of mixed groups of policy actors at the international level and the other type(s) of stakeholder(s) relevant to national-level research activities, in order to allow cross-fertilisation of ideas. Taking into account that the total number of participants will be 20-30, we foresee that a total of four break-out groups will be formed at this stage, comprised of 5-8 participants. In case the national-level stakeholders will represent more than one type of stakeholders (i.e. researchers, funders, and research managers) we will make sure that each break-out group will include all different types of national-level stakeholders. So, each type of stakeholder will be represented by at least 4 individuals.

The break-out groups will be provided with best-case and worst-case scenarios of a central topic that will have been prepared and circulated to all participants beforehand, as described in section 5.3.2. The central topic will be chosen from the collection of cases that will be compiled by WP1 in D1.4: Consolidated OA data set for responsible research practices and trust in science. The scenarios will function as an inspiration and the participants will be asked to criticise and comment the scenarios,

and not simply choose one or the other, since the purpose is to develop their personal visions (Andersen & Jæger, 1999). This part of the workshop will be directed toward vision making (City Council of Naples, 2011), providing diverse views on possible solutions to the central problem.

In the following plenary session, each break-out group, represented by a rapporteur, will present the visions that emerged from the dialogue taking place in the break-out groups. The plenum will discuss the different visions, will state objections, and eventually will clarify the components of the vision. The purpose of the plenary session is to identify the common themes underlying the visions of the different break-out groups and narrow them down to themes that will be fed into the second part.

5.3.4 Second part: Generating ideas

In the Scenario workshop's **second part**, the participants will be divided into thematic groups, which will be mixed groups comprised of participants representing all types of stakeholders, as in the case of the break-out groups of the first part of the Scenario workshop. This part of the workshop is directed toward generating ideas and providing concrete proposals (City Council of the Naples, 2011). The thematic groups will be as many as the themes decided on in the previous part and the aim for each group will be to discuss the chosen theme and develop means of action. The thematic groups will provide answers to central questions (concerning the “what”, “who” and “how” of the common themes), to develop concrete suggestions and ideas concerning the realisation of the theme under consideration (City Council of Naples, 2011).

In the following plenary session, each thematic group will present the suggestions for actions that will have been crystallised in the groups. Subsequently, the plenum will vote for the best ideas in a discussion, which should lead to results based on the consensus of all thematic groups (Gnaiger, Schroffenegger & The FBI Center, 2008).

Table 3: A tentative agenda of the Scenario workshop

Time	Topic
09:30-10:00	Welcoming and tour de table
10:00-10:30	Introduction to the aims of the workshop
10:30-10:45	Questions and answers
10:45-11:00	<i>Coffee Break</i>
Part I: Vision making	
11:00-12:00	Break-out groups
12:00-13:00	Plenary session
13:00-14:00	<i>Lunch Break</i>
Part II: Generating ideas	
14:00-15:00	Thematic groups
15:00-16:00	Plenary session
16:00-16:30	Wrap up

Figure 2: A flowchart depicting a rough plan of the Scenario workshop.

5.4 Recruitment strategy

Half of the participants at the Scenario workshop are going to be policy actors at the international level. This type of stakeholders, based on NTUA's experience, is considered as particularly challenging to recruit. As a result, the recruitment phase for this particular type of stakeholders will initiate 5 months before the Scenario workshop, i.e. from January 2025 (see section 2.7). The main communication channels that are going to be used for boosting the recruitment process are listed in Table 2.

The stakeholder type(s) that will comprise the other half of the participants will be selected on the basis of the results of D1.5, D2.5, and D3.4. Consequently, NTUA will adapt the used communication channels to boost recruitment as soon as these deliverables will have been finalised. Taking into account that the submission date of these three deliverables is M30, i.e. February 2025, there will be sufficient time to launch the recruitment process for the other types of stakeholders.

All participants will be recruited by inviting them via e-mail, starting from January 2025 for the policy actors and from February 2025 for the other type(s) of stakeholder(s). These stakeholders will have been identified either by the wide mapping exercise implemented in the context of Task 4.2 or by reaching personal contacts of POIESIS consortium members. Consequently, in order for the invitation procedure to be GDPR compliant, NTUA will use the following invitation strategy:

- Invite relevant stakeholders whose e-mail addresses are freely available on institutional websites (i.e. the ones identified in the context of Task 4.2)
- For the case of personal contacts, whose e-mail addresses are not freely available, we are going to apply the following procedure: these stakeholders are going to be initially contacted by the appropriate POIESIS consortium member (that already has their e-mail address), in order to obtain her/his permission to be invited. In case of a positive reply, NTUA is going to send the official invitation, i.e. apply the procedure of the bullet above.

NTUA is not going to use the project's e-mail address for the invitation. The invitation e-mails are going to be sent through the personal e-mail address of a member of the NTUA team.

5.5 Data collection and analysis

The different types of raw data to be collected from the Scenario WS are the following:

- Audio recordings of the whole duration of the workshop, including plenary and break-out sessions (non-anonymised)
- Flip chart notes and post-it notes (anonymised)

The audio recordings will be transcribed by the NTUA team, via a GDPR-compliant software that is going to be purchased in due time. Coding will be based on the following procedure: (a) a set of codes will be defined prior to the commencement of the Scenario workshop, based on the objectives defined from the proposal phase and on the results of D1.5, D2.5, and D3.4; (b) a set of codes will be defined after the transcription of the discussions, based on thematic analysis of emerging themes by the participants. This will allow for understanding what aspects of integrity and integration participants talked about more frequently or in depth, the ways those aspects influence societal trust in science, and how they may affect policy initiatives.

5.6 Ethical considerations

Based on the objectives of the Scenario workshop we do not expect any sensitive information to be revealed during the discussions, e.g. information relevant to the participants' health condition, religious or political beliefs. In addition, we do not expect ethical implications of the research results with regard to human dignity and integrity of the participants.

However, in order to decide whether an ethics approval should be obtained we will contact NTUA's DPO and NTUA's Research Ethics and Deontology Committee close to the end of the second year of POIESIS, in order to have enough time to develop all potentially needed informed consent forms and informative material relevant to data management before the commencement of the recruitment period. We do not foresee a need for a Joint Data Controller Agreement, since all data will be collected and analysed by NTUA. In case of a change of plans, i.e. in case of involvement of another partner in the process of data collection and analysis a Joint Data Controller Agreement is going to be signed by all involved consortium partners.

5.7 Division of responsibilities

NTUA will have the main responsibility for the design, organisation, and conduct of the Scenario workshop, as well as the collection and analysis of data. The following partners are expected to contribute:

- **AU** in the design of the coding strategy and on relevant methodological issues
- Leaders of WPs 1-3, i.e. **WiD**, **ISCTE**, and **CNRS**, in order to aid NTUA define the type(s) of relevant stakeholder(s) from national-level research activities that best fit the needs of the Scenario workshop
- **All POIESIS partners** in the collection of individual invitees to the Scenario workshop.

6 Deviations from DoA

There are no deviations from the DoA.

References

Andersen, I.-E., & Jæger, B. (1999). Scenario workshops and consensus conferences: Towards more democratic decision-making. *Science and Public Policy*, 26(5), 331-340. doi:10.3152/147154399781782301

City Council of Naples (Ed.). (2011, July). The waterfront of the historic centre and port area from piazza Municipio to piazza Mercato: a sustainable development. Naples. Retrieved September 22, 2022, from URBACT: <https://urbact.eu/ctur-naples-activities-ulsq-spotlight>

European Awareness Scenario Workshops. (1997, May 29). European Union. Retrieved September 22, 2022, from CORDIS: <https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/8356-european-awareness-scenario-workshops>

Gnaiger, A., Schroffenegger, G., & The FBI Center (Eds.). (2008). *"Tool-Kit Scenario Workshop"*. TRAMS: Training and Mentoring of Science Shops. Innsbruck: The FBI Center.

Oreszczyn, S., & Carr, S. (2008). Improving the link between policy research and practice: using a scenario workshop as a qualitative research tool in the case of genetically modified crops. *Qualitative Research*, 8(4), 473-497. doi:10.1177/1468794107087479